

Pencil-Lead-Based Quasi-Equilibrium Glucose Biosensors

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Foreign body response is the main reason for the limited lifetime of implantable glucose biosensors. A new measurement strategy exerting minimal disturbance from the equilibrium glucose concentration in the sensor compartment has been proposed to mitigate its adverse effects on the sensor signal. Here, a new measurement strategy using automatically fabricated and robust pencil-lead-based glucose biosensors is implemented. The sensor response depends on critical parameters such as redox-polymer film thickness, film uniformity, rigidity, polymer composition, and the ratio between the enzyme and the polymer. These parameters are controlled by introducing a short-chain redox polymer, a low crosslinker amount, a short-chain electrografting agent and linker, pulse electrografting, and an automated fabrication procedure.

1. Introduction

The challenge of developing implantable glucose biosensors with prolonged functionality remains unresolved. The existing commercially available subcutaneously implanted glucose biosensors typically exhibit a limited operational lifespan, not surpassing 180 days.^[1] Besides the intrinsic stability of the biological recognition element, typically an enzyme, the most significant contribution to the loss of accuracy and lifetime is the foreign body response (FBR), resulting in biofouling and loss of the signal.^[2,3] In the sensing layer of such a biosensor, glucose is continuously consumed, creating a concentration gradient, and glucose is replenished from the external environment by diffusional mass transport. The diffusional flux is slowed down by increasing the encapsulation layers formed due to the FBR, hence lowering the apparent glucose concentration in the sensing layer and decreasing the sensor response. Recently, our group

introduced an alternative measurement concept that does not depend on a continuous catalytic substrate conversion and, therefore, could circumvent the challenges leading to the shortened operation of glucose biosensors due to the FBR.^[4] The proposed concept involves three key strategies in designing a new sensor type: 1) switching off the catalytic turnover reaction; 2) mitigating uncontrollable parasitic reactions, such as oxygen reduction; and 3) minimizing substrate concentration disturbances during measurements to maintain quasi-equilibrium conditions.

Potential pulses controlling the turnover capability of the used enzyme in combination with open-circuit potential (OCP) measurements were employed to achieve minimal disturbance of the substrate equilibrium and prevent parasitic reactions during measurement (**Figure 1**).^[4] It could be demonstrated that for an oxygen-insensitive enzyme, which is immobilized on an electrode solely by means of a redox polymer, switching off of enzyme turnover can be achieved by applying a potential that is 250 mV lower than the formal potential of the polymer-bound redox moieties, a situation which we named “off” pulse.^[4] Applying the off-pulse potential keeps the Os-complexes at the redox polymer in a reduced state, meaning that the enzyme turnover is deactivated while the system remains in this state. Conversely, activation is achieved when the applied potential is 250 mV higher than the formal potential of the polymer-bound redox moieties, a situation which we named “on” pulse.^[4] During the on-pulse, the Os-complexes are oxidized, enabling reoxidation of the prosthetic group within the active center of the polymer-entrapped enzyme and thus enzymatic turnover. The on-pulse should only last sufficiently long to charge the redox hydrogel without creating a significant concentration gradient between the concentration of glucose in the sensor compartment and the implantation site. After enzyme activation, the electrical circuit is switched off, and the modulation of the open-circuit potential is measured potentiometrically, enabling the determination of the glucose concentration-dependent potential decay over time. Previous studies have established that OCP biosensors exhibit size- and interference-independent performance.^[5–7]

These principles were previously effectively implemented in a redox hydrogel-based catalytic microbiosensor using an O₂-independent flavin-dependent glucose dehydrogenase (FAD-GDH).^[4] However, the size of the sensor and the complexity of its fabrication pose challenges to applying such a system for widespread use directly. We propose a more robust configuration of the sensor based on a pencil-lead electrode. The larger size of the electrode introduces challenges to achieve control over crucial

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DOI: 10.1002/adsr.202400024

Figure 1. Parameters influencing the sensor signal arising from the glucose measurement (ON) phase (green) and equilibrium (OFF) phase.

parameters such as film thickness, uniformity, rigidity, polymer composition, and the ratio between the enzyme and the polymer (Figure 1), which is necessary to ensure a reproducible glucose-concentration correlated sensor signal.

2. Results and Discussion

Our initial investigations revealed that two parasitic processes influence the measurement significantly when the sensor dimensions are enlarged from micro to submillimeter size, preventing accurate measurement of enzymatic turnover and thus glucose concentration, namely, the ion diffusion modulated by polymer swelling and electron hopping through the polymer that competes with the electron exchange between the polymer-entrapped enzyme and redox species bound to the polymer.

The kinetics of polymer rearrangement seem to exhibit notable sluggishness on the macro-scale in thicker polymer films (Figure S1, Supporting Information). During a short potential pulse, a thick film cannot be completely charged, leading to a decay of the Nernst potential over time that is not related to the signal from enzymatic glucose oxidation. Consequently, the off-pulse duration as well as the short preliminary conditioning of the system as employed in our prior study^[4] do not help to overcome this issue. The kinetics of this process depend on several parameters, such as the mobility of the polymer chains and the degree of swelling of the film in the solution. The degree of swelling depends on film thickness, local pH changes due to glucose oxidation to gluconic acid, and counterion movement, while the mobility of the polymer chains depends on the conformation of the polymer and the degree of cross-linking. Following these considerations, we attempted, on the one hand, to find an optimal polymer-film thickness, and on the other hand, to reduce the polymer-chain length since long-chain polymers tend to form low-mobile globules.

2.1. Synthesis of Short-Chain Redox Polymers

Small changes were implemented in the redox polymer preparation procedure to obtain shorter chain polymers of the commonly

used Os-complex modified redox polymer—poly(vinyl imidazole-co-allylamine)-osmium bis(2,2'-bipyridine)chloride (further P(VI-AA)-[Os(bpy)₂Cl]⁺).^[8] First, the backbone was synthesized via free-radical polymerization with azobis(isobutyronitrile) (AIBN) as a radical initiator.^[8–10] Polymer chains of a desired molecular weight (between 3 and 10 kDa) were obtained by ultrafiltration. Afterward, the short-chain polymer backbone was complexed with osmium bis(2,2'-bipyridine)chloride (Figure 2). The resulting polymer chains are ten times shorter than those determined for polyvinylimidazole.^[10] Additionally, the control of the molecular weight by ultrafiltration resulted in a narrower molecular weight distribution, enhancing the uniformity of the polymer film.

2.2. Pulsed Electrografting

The graphite of the pencil lead was functionalized with amino groups by oxidative electrografting to increase the stability of the redox hydrogel film on the graphite surface.^[11,12] The electrode modification is performed via electrochemical diamine oxidation under the formation of covalent C–N bonds.^[12] The free amino group later reacts with electrophilic groups in the polymer, forming a covalently attached film. The standard electrografting procedure uses cyclic voltammetry scans to perform electrooxidation,^[12–14] however, we employed pulse chronoamperometry which allows for replenishing the high diamine concentration near the electrode while applying the no-effect potential. Moreover, this saves time during electrografting, thus making the whole process more efficient.

The diamine connecting the graphite surface and the redox polymer has also been changed compared with the previous protocol.^[4] When the two amino groups of 1,7-diaminoheptane are not protected, they might loop and react with the electrode surface, and block it instead of staying available for linking with the epoxide-containing redox polymer. Also, the length of the non-conductive heptane chain could potentially slow down the electron transfer. For this reason, tert-butyloxycarbonyl

Figure 2. Synthesis of short-chain P(VI-AA)-[Os(bpy)₂Cl]⁺. Synthesis of the poly(vinyl imidazole-co-allylamine) by means of free radical polymerization followed by separation of the desired molecular weight fraction (between 3 and 10 kDa) by ultrafiltration. Synthesis of the redox polymer by complexing the polymer backbone and osmium bis(2,2'-bipyridine)chloride.

(Boc)-protected ethylenediamine was used for electrografting, and butanediol-diglycidyl ether (BDGE) was used instead of poly(ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether (PEGDGE) as the linker between the amino-functionalized pencil-lead surface and the redox polymer. The final architecture of the biosensor is shown in Figure 3.

2.3. Automated Fabrication of the Modified Pencil-Lead Biosensors

A common way to control the polymer film thickness is to use a manual layer-by-layer dip coating technique. As the time scale of each dipping step lies within seconds, the human factor severely changes the repeatability of the electrode preparation. Hence, we

implemented an automatic dip-coating strategy using a positioning element moveable in x-, y-, and z-directions by step-motor-driven micrometer screws (Figure 3). Additionally, to enhance the efficiency and reproducibility of the sensor preparation, multiple sensors were prepared simultaneously using a specifically developed multiple-electrodes holder in combination with a multi-potentiostat.

As the thickness and rigidity of the film should noticeably affect the kinetics of film re-arrangement,^[15,16] we attempted to optimize these two parameters. The original sensor consisted of three layers, and the concentration of the crosslinker in the dipping solution was 5 mg mL⁻¹ (Figure 4).^[4]

Implementing a short-chain polymer together with an automatic fabrication strategy does not lead to the desired sensor

Figure 3. Scheme of the pencil-lead sensor architecture. The tip of a 0.3 mm pencil lead insulated by a pipette tip and inserted in a conductive pencil-based holder is modified by electrografting with ethylene diamine, which subsequently reacts with the linker (BDGE), followed by subsequent dip-coating in redox polymer (P(VI-AA)-[Os(bpy)₂Cl]⁺) and enzyme (FAD-GDH) solutions and finally crosslinking with a bifunctional crosslinking agent (PEGDGE).

Figure 4. Automatized sensor fabrication setup. Pulsed electrografting with N-Boc-ethylene diamine (deprotection of Boc-groups in acidic media not depicted) followed by layer-by-layer dip-coating consisting of the following steps: 1) BGDE solution; 2) P(VI-AA)-[Os(bpy)₂Cl]⁺ solution; 3) FAD-GDH solution; 4) P(VI-AA)-[Os(bpy)₂Cl]⁺ solution; 5) PEGDGE crosslinker solution; 6) washing in phosphate buffer.

Figure 5. OCP potential transients of an automatically fabricated 12-layer sensor. The duration of the off-pulse was 37 s, that of the charging pulse 0.5 s, and the potential transients were recorded during 0.1 s at OCP. The potential during the off-pulse was -0.5 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 m KCl, and the potential during the on-pulse was 0.45 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 m KCl. A) Potential transients (60 cycles). B) Slopes of individual potential transients versus cycle number.

response of the film (Figure. S2). After testing various layer numbers and crosslinker concentrations, we found that the optimal sensor architecture consists of 12 layers, and the PEGDGE crosslinker amount should be 1 mg mL^{-1} (Figure. S3, Supporting Information). Furthermore, optimal results are obtained by mixing the enzyme, polymer, and crosslinker for the dip-coating process. Using a homogeneous mixture for dip-coating previously led to a fast aggregation of polymer and enzyme upon mixing. However, using the shorter-chain polymer minimizes the aggregation process and allows using a homogeneous enzyme-polymer-crosslinker mixture for dip-coating for increased layer uniformity and reproducibility (Figure. S4, Supporting Information).

2.4. Optimization of the Measuring Sequence

As previously discussed,^[4] conditioning under constant oxidative potential serves as a step during which the film adapts to the surrounding environment. While a 1 min conditioning was enough

for microbiosensors,^[4] such constant potential conditioning is inefficient for stabilizing the hydrogel swelling. Therefore, we suggest a multi-pulse potentiometric measurement for sensor conditioning similar to the sequence employed for glucose determination.

The measurement procedure consisted of a longer switching-off pulse, a shorter switching-on pulse, and a short OCP measurement. Moreover, after an envisaged implantation, the sensor would be exposed to interstitial fluid or even whole blood conditions, and hence glucose is always present, conditioning was performed in glucose solution. Potential transients (Figure 5A) as well as the slopes of the potential transients, calculated at the first 20 ms (Figure 5B), overlap after 50–60 cycles, which is considered as sufficiently preconditioned sensor properties.

Despite increasing the size of the sensor, we managed to decrease the measurement time. Microsized sensors described previously required 90 s of off-pulse time for the solution within the film to be exchanged and 1 s of on-pulse time to activate a sufficient amount of the enzyme.^[4] Figure 6 shows how different

Figure 6. OCP potential transients of the automatically fabricated 12-layer sensor. The duration of the regeneration time (off-pulse) was varied from 1 to 75 s. The duration of the charging pulse was 0.5 s, the measuring time at OCP was 0.1 s. The potential during the off-pulse was -0.5 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 m KCl, and the potential during the on-pulse was 0.45 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 m KCl.

off-pulse times ranging from 1 to 75 s affect the sensor performance. At the shortest off-pulse time of 1 s, there is no difference between the sensor responses to different glucose concentrations. Most likely, this time is too short for equilibration of the glucose concentration between the sensor compartment and the solution. When the solution was exchanged for phosphate buffer, the potential transients did not overlap, suggesting a rearrangement of polymer-film swelling, which may last longer than 1 s. These issues were mitigated with longer off-pulse durations. The most significant difference between the sensor responses to 5 and 10 mM glucose concentrations was reached when the off-pulse time was 37 s. Hence, this off-pulse duration was chosen for all further experiments.

2.5. Final Sensor Configuration

An additional protective layer was introduced covering the redox polymer film, comprising a zwitterionic polymer consisting of 2-methacryloyloxyethyl phosphorylcholine (MPC) copolymerized with glycidyl methacrylate (GMA) (referred to as MPC polymer). This additional layer minimizes the leakage of the enzyme and the redox polymer and has been shown to reduce biofouling and cell adhesion.^[17,18] Additionally, the drying time of the sensor, which also is essential for the crosslinking between the crosslinker PEGDGE and the polymer backbone, was changed from one day to a two-phase procedure: one day at room temperature, application of the supplementary MPC layer, followed by drying over 5 days at 4 °C. The difference between potential

transients for different glucose concentrations, along with the calculated differences in slopes within the time range of 0–20 ms, was most significant for this sensor configuration (Figure 7). This demonstrates the influence of the enzymatic reaction on potential decay (for the potential decay without the enzymatic reaction, Figure S5, Supporting Information), surpassing the impact of parasitic processes, as depicted in Figure 7.

3. Conclusion

An automatized preparation procedure of robust pencil-lead-based catalytic glucose biosensors operating under substrate concentration equilibrium conditions is demonstrated. For the performance of the pencil lead electrode-based biosensors consisting of O_2 -insensitive FAD-GDH, Os-complex modified redox polymer, and a zwitterionic MPC-based capping layer, a number of factors are critical, namely the polymer-film thickness and uniformity, the film rigidity, and the ratio between enzyme and polymer. After determining the crucial parameters influencing the sensor signal, we developed an optimal sensor configuration for the more robust pencil-lead size. A short-chain polymer with a molecular weight distribution below 10 kDa was used to increase the film uniformity and to decrease the thickness of one dip-coated layer. Diamine electrografting for functionalization of the pencil-lead surface was optimized using pulsed chronoamperometry instead of cyclic voltammetry, followed by an automated dip-coating procedure in a mixture of the polymer, the enzyme, and the crosslinker. Additionally, a shorter 1,4-butanediol diglycidyl ether linker between the ethylenediamine-modified

Figure 7. OCP potential transients of the automatically fabricated 12-layer sensor. The duration of the off-pulse was 37 s. The duration of the charging pulse was 0.5 s, the measuring time at OCP was 0.1 s. The potential during the off-pulse was -0.5 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 m KCl, the potential during the on-pulse was 0.45 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 m KCl. A) OCP potential transients; B) Slopes of individual OCP potential transients versus measurement time.

graphite electrode surface and the polymer matrix was chosen. A conditioning step involving multi-pulse chronopotentiometry in the presence of glucose was implemented for the stabilization of the redox hydrogel. Corresponding sensors subjected to nearly 1 h of conditioning in the presence of glucose exhibit a noteworthy distinction in potential transients across varying glucose concentrations. With an on-pulse duration of 0.75 s and an off-pulse duration of 37 s, the overall measurement cycle duration is sufficiently short for the necessary frequency of glucose detection for in vivo sensors.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: All chemicals were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich. Recombinant FAD-dependent glucose dehydrogenase (FAD-GDH) from *Glomerella cingulata* was provided by Prof. Roland Ludwig, BOKU, Austria. All electrochemical experiments were carried out at room temperature under ambient conditions. All aqueous solutions were prepared using ultrapure water. The MPC coating was synthesized as previously described.^[17] NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker DRX400 spectrometer with a proton resonance frequency of 400.13 MHz. The residual solvent peak served as an internal standard.

Synthesis of poly(1-vinylimidazole-co-allylamine): The synthesis of the polymer backbone was conducted by adapting a procedure reported previously.^[9] The co-monomers allylamine (0.4 mL, 5.33 mmol) and 1-vinylimidazole (6 mL, 66.24 mmol), as well as the initiator 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionitrile) (AIBN) (0.48 g, 2.92 mmol) were mixed and heated to 70 °C using an oil bath and under heavy stirring under argon atmosphere. After ≈ 30 min, the gel was allowed to cool down to room temperature. The polymer was extracted with ethanol, and insoluble remains were discarded. The yellow ethanol phase was poured into 1 L of acetone, and the polymer was precipitated by adding diethyl ether. The yellowish precipitate was collected and dissolved in ethanol (100 mL) again. The alcohol phase was quenched with 500 mL of diethyl ether, and the precipitate was collected via filtration. The product was dried in an oven at 75–80 °C to yield 1.13 g ($\approx 20\%$ yield) of a pale-yellow crystalline powder.

¹H-NMR (400.13 MHz, MeOD- d_3): 7.11, 6.86, and 6.80 (multiple signals, imidazole units, 3H), 3.19, 2.98, and 2.89 (broad, overlapping, $-\text{CH}-$ units in backbone, 1H), 2.11 and 1.98 (broad, $-\text{CH}_2-$ units in backbone, 2H), 0.94 (allylamine, 0.06H)

The dried polymer was dissolved in water. The solution was filtered with a Vivaspin20 ultrapurification unit by centrifugation with a molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) of 10 kDa. The filtrate was filtered again with

a Vivaspin20 unit with a 3 kDa MWCO. The residue that did not pass the filter was collected and dried under reduced pressure.

The Synthesis of poly(vinyl imidazole-co-allylamine)-osmium bis(2,2'-bipyridine)Chloride: The synthesis was conducted according to the protocol from ref.[8] with a slight variation. In a Schlenk tube (with pressure compensation) and an under argon atmosphere, the short-chain fraction of the polymer backbone poly(vinyl imidazole-co-allylamine) was mixed with Os(bpy) $_2$ Cl $_2$ in a molar ratio of 1:10. The mixture was suspended in ethylene glycol, then deaerated under vacuum until bubbles stopped appearing, flushed with argon, and heated to 80 °C for 5 days. Afterward, it was cooled down to room temperature.

The solution was poured into 100 mL ethyl acetate, and then 20 mL acetone was added as a solvent mediator. The solvent was decanted off, and the dark red oily/sticky residue was dissolved in 20 mL of ethanol. The alcohol phase was poured into 200 mL of diethyl ether, forming a red-brown precipitate. The major part of the solvent was decanted off, and the residue was separated by centrifugation (4000 rpm, 5 min). The polymer was first washed with diethyl ether (100 mL) and centrifuged again. Finally, the polymer was washed with *tert*-butyl methyl ether (100 mL), centrifuged, and air-dried. The dark brown polymer was dried at r.t. over the weekend.

The obtained short-chain redox polymer was purified from residues of the unreacted Os complex by Vivaspin20 ultrafiltration with a centrifuge using a membrane of 3 kDa MWCO. The precipitate was collected from the membrane. It was transferred to an Eppendorf tube, frozen in liquid nitrogen, and dried under vacuum overnight.

Electrode Preparation: Graphite pencil leads (Staedtler Mars micro carbon), marked as HB (“medium hard” or “hard black”), were used as electrodes. They are supposed to have a diameter of 350 μm . However, the diameter varied in the range of 350–365 μm as determined by an optical microscope. The electrode was inserted in the plastic tip for Eppendorf pipettes of 20 μL . Then, the end of the tip was melted so that the graphite was glued into it. Afterward, the electrode was polished with sandpaper (roughness 991) until its length was 1 mm \pm 50 μm .

Electrografting: Electrografting was conducted in a three-electrode cell with a pseudo-Ag reference electrode (i.e., Ag wire covered with AgCl) and a Pt counter electrode. A solution of 0.015 M *N*-Boc-ethylenediamine (NBocEDA) and 0.15 M tetrabutylammonium tetrafluoroborate (TBAF $_4$) in commercial dry acetonitrile from Sigma–Aldrich was used as electrolyte. The solution was stored for up to one week. Pulsed chronoamperometry measurements were conducted for 5 \times 30 s pulses to a potential of 1.1 V versus Ag/AgCl and 5 \times 30 s pulses of 0 V versus Ag/AgCl. The holder of the pens with graphite is moved across the solution between each pulse. The movement time is 2 s.

Automated Dip-Coating: To perform automated dip-coating, the manipulator, moveable in x-, y-, and z-axis was used by step-motors (Owis). The mixture for dip-coating was poured into a sterilized new microplate 96/U with a round form of cavities, volume 360 μL . The movement was

controlled using the in-house written software “Union”. The mixture of the polymer, the enzyme, and poly(ethyleneglycol)diglycidylether (PEGDGE) was prepared freshly before dip-coating. The concentration of the components in the mixture was: 1.25 mg mL⁻¹ of P(VI-AA)-[Os(bpy)₂Cl]⁺, 2.5 mg mL⁻¹ FAD-GDH, 1 mg mL⁻¹ of PEGDGE. Solutions of BDGE and phosphate buffer (PB) could be stored for over a month at room temperature. The electrolyte for electrografting based on NBocEDA, TBABF₄, and acetonitrile could be stored at room temperature or in the fridge for 1 week.

After electrografting, an electrode was immediately dipped in 4 M HCl/dioxane for 5 min. Then, it was washed by dipping for 1 min in absolute ethanol and ultrapure water sequentially. Next, it was immersed in 5 mg mL⁻¹ BDGE solution for 10 min and then dried in air for 20 min. Afterward, a pencil lead was repetitively immersed in the polymer-enzyme-crosslinker mixture for 30 s with 1 min pauses for drying. The optimal number of layers was 12. Then, the sensor was dried overnight in the air. The next day, it was immersed in 10 mg mL⁻¹ MPC solution for 1 min and left to dry at 4 °C for 5 more days.

Glucose Concentration Measurement: A three-electrode cell was used comprising a Pt wire electrode as counter electrode (CE) and a self-made Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl as reference electrode (RE) (Figure S6, Supporting Information). The CE and RE are not separated from the working electrode by any membrane or frit. A plastic 5 mL Petri dish was used as a vessel for the electrolyte. When the concentration of glucose in the solution was changed, the solution was mixed with a pipette. The potential shift of the reference electrode was monitored before each set of measurements. The cell was assembled with the potentiostat being disconnected. An Autolab type III/FRA2 potentiostat/galvanostat from Metrohm Autolab controlled with Nova 1.11 was used to perform the measurements. The Autolab potentiostat was set to the high-speed regime. Two cycles of cyclic voltammetry in the voltage range from -0.05 to 0.45 V were measured at a scan rate of 0.01 V s⁻¹. The starting potential is -0.05 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl. Then, different variations of multi-pulse potentiometry were conducted. During the off-pulse, a reducing potential of -0.05 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl was applied. The typical off-pulse duration is 37 s; however, for some experiments, the off-pulse duration was varied. Then, the on-pulse at + 0.45 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl is applied. The time of this pulse was varied in several experiments across the range: 1, 0.75, 0.5, 0.2, 0.1 s. At last, chronopotentiometric measurements in the high-speed regime at OCP were performed for 0.5 s. The recording speed is 1 point per ms during the potentiometric data acquisition. Before these cycles, a potential of -0.05 V versus Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl was applied for 10 s to charge the graphite part of the working electrode.

Pre-Processing of Data: All measurement values and related graphs in the manuscript are based on the original data without any data transformation or noise reduction. Using these original data, the slope of the regression line between 0 and 20 ms was calculated.

Data Presentation: Statistical variation of four measurements of five increasing glucose concentrations obtained with the same sensor are shown in Figure S7 (Supporting Information).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

S.S. and A.L. contributed equally to this work. The authors are grateful for financial support from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie MSCA-ITN “Im-

plantSens” [813006]. The authors are thankful to Prof. Dr. Roland Ludwig, BOKU—University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna; for the provision of the FAD-GDH. The authors would also like to thank Dr. Anna Muhs for helpful discussions regarding the technical and scientific implementation of the experiments.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

FAD-GDH, glucose biosensors, potentiometry, pulse measurement

Received: February 11, 2024

Revised: May 11, 2024

Published online:

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